

MODERN METHODS IN LEARNING ENGLISH

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Abstract. *Communication in any language involves pronunciation, intonation, comprehension and knowledge of the colloquial dialect and slang. To practice English fluency in real-world situations, English language students -- whether native or non-native - benefit from learning essential*

Keywords: *method, character, effect, modern, impact, society, learn, participatory, knowledge, situation, development.*

СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. *Общение на любом языке предполагает произношение, интонацию, понимание и знание разговорного диалекта и сленга. Чтобы практиковать свободное владение английским языком в реальных ситуациях, студенты, изучающие английский язык, независимо от того, являются ли они носителями языка или не носителями языка, извлекают пользу из изучения основных*

Ключевые слова: *метод, характер, эффект, современный, воздействие, общество, обучение, участие, знание, ситуация, развитие.*

We will present some methods that is developing observation skills. Skits. Come up with a dialogue for a skit between students. Choose a topic or theme, such as family vacation, first day of school year, camping or sleepover. You can also come up with a conflict for each story, such as, in the family vacation topic, missing the flight for the destination. If your students are at a more advanced English language level, allow them to come up with a dialogue together. Ask the students to get into character to play their parts. For example, in the family example, each student may play a role like the mother, father, brother and sister. They will communicate with each other about what to do since they missed their flight. Encourage creativity, humor and dramatic effect.

Games. Play games that feature English words and popular phrases. For example, board games that feature plays on words, catch phrases and popular quotes from English-language TV shows and movies is a fun way for students to learn English phrases. However, other quieter board games, like Scrabble, help the students build English vocabulary to help with communication. If you are tutoring a student, or students, feel free to help students find words in the letter tiles.

Creative Writing “Exquisite Corpse”. Organize students into small groups for a creative writing exercise. Give each group a topic, such as phone conversation, writing home, preparing for a soccer game or snow day. One person in each group will write one sentence with less than 15 words on a lined sheet of paper. When she finishes writing her sentence on the topic, she folds the paper over so the next person cannot see her sentence. After a few circulations, stop the exercise and let everyone read the sentences all together. It’s likely the “story” won’t make sense. Encourage students to put the sentences in an order that does make sense for effective communication in English. For instance, a student may write, in the phone conversation topic, “Hi, Sarah! I just got home from school. How are you?” and another student may write, “I’m

calling to let you know...I passed the test!” Then students can re-order the sentences in a way they feel is best.

Movie Clip Project. Ask students to make up believable dialogues for characters in the movie clips you show. For instance, if you show the scene in “The Wizard of Oz” when Dorothy first lands in Oz, you can create a made-up dialogue for Dorothy and the good queen. If you show a clip from “The Beauty and the Beast,” students can create a conversation between Belle and the Beast. Students may write the dialogue on a separate sheet of paper. Be sure to keep the movie on mute. If you want to show the actual dialogue between characters, you can show the clips in full sound after the exercises. An important question for every society - and most particularly for emerging as well as established democracies - is how to educate the young so that they become competent, responsible, and knowledgeable citizens. That is a challenge of overriding importance. Not only does the quality of life in a democracy depend upon how well that challenge is met. So, too, does the stability - indeed, the endurance of democracy itself is contingent on the competence, commitment, and caring of its citizens.

An infant may be born a citizen in the eyes of the law, but transforming a human being into a citizen who can participate effectively and responsibly in a democratic society is a lengthy and demanding task. Fortunately, we now can turn for guidance about how to accomplish that task to a growing body of research. Because of constraints on time, we would like to draw your attention to a very small portion of that research - findings which are indicative of what we now know about the effectiveness of modern methods of learning and learning. But before we turn to the research findings, let’s remind ourselves that the objective of civic education is not to make all students into adults exclusively or obsessively occupied with political matters or who participate intensively and continuously on every conceivable issue. In a democratic society each individual must retain the right to choose where, when, and how he or she wishes to participate. Without the requisite knowledge and skills, however, an incompetent citizen has only two options. We believe that schools should open a third option to all students: to participate in ways that are effective and which accord with democratic values and procedures. What does research tell us about how to make that third option a viable one? By far the most important finding to emerge from the study, one that applies equally to adult and school-based programs, is that course design and the quality of instruction are critical to the success of civic education programs. If civic education programs are well-designed and well taught, if they meet frequently, use participatory methods, stress learning by doing, and focus on issues that have direct relevance to participants’ daily lives, they can have a significant, positive impact on democratic participation and attitudes.

Additional evidence on the effectiveness of modern methods of learning comes from a report entitled *The Civic Mission of Schools*. It is a consensus document developed by respected researchers and practitioners which set out what research shows are six promising practices schools can employ to develop competent and responsible citizens. The first promising practice is formal instruction in government, history, and democracy to increase civic knowledge. That is an important goal in itself, because as abundant research has shown “For those who are relatively well-informed, the system operates much as in textbook descriptions of representative democracy. The less informed one is, however, the less likely one is to participate, and the less likely it is that one’s participation will be effective. The modern methods of the group have important impact on the way of thinking and acting of children. Their application is made as a game with rules. Presented in this way, the methods convince the children to participate to the activity, for an active learning and cooperation and determine them to collaborate inside the group. The teachers should know how to use these modern group-work methods taking into consideration the different personalities of the children. Each child needs a special gesture, questions, advice, motivation and attitude depending on the situation.

The following tips should be followed each time we apply team-work plays: - The period of time for the activity has to be mentioned to the children. - The steps and rules of the activity should be presented gradually. - The activity has to be connected to the reality. - The activity has to offer to the children the possibility of feed-back, of correcting themselves.

Learning English through modern methods in elementary classes Children learn English as a second or foreign language much faster than the adults. They imitate the teacher's pronunciation, sentences, phrases, and words more easily. They do not ask for explicit rules which explain how sentences are put together, produced, and pronounced. They may ask for the meanings of words, but they are able to intuitively identify salient features of the meanings of a word and use the word more or less correctly.

An important prerequisite for effective learning and retention appears to be that instruction should be activity-based, rather than explanation- or theory-oriented. And the activities should be of an engaging nature. We, the teacher, should be pleasant and sweet-natured, able to communicate at the level of the children. We should not be a terror! Use of audio-visuals is more important than the printed text. The printed text should be colorful, full of pictures, and should have only few language elements such as words, phrases, and sentences. Language learning should be encouraged in all the classes and in all the environments. Children have a natural curiosity to investigate the environment in greater detail. When they go to the bazaar, they see a lot of signboards and they start reading the same. They start reading the road signs with great interest. We can create a bazaar inside the classroom for reading and conversation purposes. Pretend situations are greatly enjoyed by children, and they do actively participate in such games.

In conclusion, we believe that this process can fully improve students' ideation and practical language skills, which is helpful and useful to ensure and fulfill an effective result of learning and learning. Barring a few problem areas multimedia technology can be used effectively in classrooms of ELT with proper computer knowledge on the part of teachers, overcoming the finance problems in setting up the infrastructure and not allowing the teachers to become technophobes. Learning materials should be seen as a dynamic part of the learning process and not just something given out to learners with no follow-up or input from the teacher or facilitator. The principles of adult learning should be incorporated into their development and use, so that they are practical, problem oriented and relevant to the learners' situation and learning needs. A variety of learning materials should be used to encourage learning for knowledge, attitudes and skills. Written materials may not be the most appropriate, particularly for health education programmes, other media should be considered and used. The participatory approach to the use of learning materials will not only improve retention of the learning but also increase the attitude and performance skills learning.

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